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ABSTRACT

Touch-enabled technologies, from smartphones to public kiosks, are ubiquitous, yet frequent use turns their surfaces into reservoirs for microbial contamination. Routine alcohol-based cleaning can be impractical on high-touch optical surfaces due to damage risk and usability concerns. Here, we present a scalable approach to transparent, mechanically robust glass surfaces by embedding materials with *ad hoc* functionality into surface glass nanoholes. We demonstrate the concept with copper nanodisks: copper is an established antimicrobial agent, but its wear susceptibility pose challenges for use on transparent displays. Our design shields the functional material from lateral wear while allowing ion diffusion for antimicrobial efficacy. Fabrication uses only wafer-compatible, lithography-free steps: thermal dewetting of a thin silver film to create a nanosized mask; inverting it to a polymer nanoholes mask by etching the silver nanoparticles; wet etching of the glass to form nanoholes; selective copper deposition inside these holes; and liftoff of excess material. The resulting surfaces exhibit mean transmission of 80%–85% in the 380–750 nm range with haze <1% and minimal color shift, compared to uncoated glass. Antimicrobial efficacy, assessed against *Escherichia coli* OP50 under a modified U.S. EPA protocol, shows ≈99% bacterial reduction within one hour. Abrasion tests with a crockmeter simulating finger swipes confirm that the embedded copper remains intact, with no measurable change in optical performance. This embedded design provides a scalable route to integrate antimicrobial functionality into high-touch transparent systems while preserving optical clarity and wear resistance, with potential relevance for medical, consumer, and transportation interfaces.

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I. INTRODUCTION

High-touch surfaces, such as mobile devices, touchscreen displays, and public kiosks, are essential to daily life yet act as reservoirs for harmful micro-organisms.^{1,2} Frequent handling of such devices significantly contributes to microbial contamination and the transmission of infectious diseases, contributing to both healthcare-associated and community-acquired infections.³ Traditional alcohol-based disinfection, although somewhat effective, is often impractical in high-touch environments, such as healthcare

settings and public spaces, because of frequent use and the risk of damaging sensitive devices.⁴ With the rise of antibiotic-resistant bacteria, such as *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) and *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*),⁵ there is increasing demand for antimicrobial (AM) transparent surfaces and coatings that inhibit microbial growth upon contact. Balancing multiple competing requirements simultaneously such as optical transparency, low haze, high AM efficacy, durability under wear, and non-conductivity to maintain touchscreen functionality remains a major challenge.

Mechanobactericidal surfaces feature biomimetic nanospikes or nanopillars that physically rupture microbial membranes via nanoscale puncture or tension.^{6–10} While effective in certain applications, their bactericidal performance relies heavily on high-aspect-ratio features that are inherently fragile under lateral abrasion.¹¹ In addition, fabrication typically requires complex lithography that limits scalability to large-area substrates¹² and often degrades optical clarity through scattering, constraining use on transparent touch interfaces.

Transition metals, their oxides, and metal/metal oxide nanoparticles represent another widely studied class of AM agents.^{3,13–25} Copper (Cu) and silver (Ag) have been used for water preservation and food treatment since ancient times,²⁶ long before their bactericidal mechanism was understood.²⁷ Cu, in particular, exhibits multifaceted bactericidal mechanisms.^{3,15,17} Cu^+ and Cu^{2+} ions, generated through water corrosion processes, interact with negatively charged domains on bacterial membranes, reducing the potential difference across the membrane and causing depolarization, membrane leakiness, or rupture when the potential difference drops to zero.¹⁵ In addition, Cu ions catalyze the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS), including hydrogen peroxide, hydroxyl radicals, superoxide, and singlet oxygen, via Fenton-like reactions.^{3,13} These ROS initiate oxidative stress, leading to lipid peroxidation, protein denaturation, and DNA damage, ultimately disrupting cellular processes and causing bacterial death.^{3,13,15} These properties make Cu an ideal AM material, particularly for high-touch applications.

Other metal-containing approaches have been developed to incorporate AM agents into transparent coatings or glass substrates. Photocatalytic metal oxides, such as titanium dioxide (TiO_2)²⁸ and zinc oxide (ZnO),²⁹ produce ROS upon activation by light and moisture, providing sustained AM activity. However, their dependency on light limits their effectiveness in indoor environments. Alternative approaches include ion-exchanged glass with diffusive layers of Ag ions, which have demonstrated antibacterial efficacy against *S. aureus*,³⁰ and Ag nanoparticles embedded in polycarbonate substrates, which offer scalability for mass production.³¹ Hybrid polymer coatings represent another promising avenue for AM surface design, combining transparency, durability, and multifunctionality.^{32–34} For example, zinc oxide-polytetrafluoroethylene (ZnO-PTFE)³⁵ and polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE)-coated zinc-doped silicon oxide (SZO/PTFE)³⁶ composite thin films have demonstrated antibacterial activity, hydrophobicity, and antireflective properties, making them suitable for touchscreen devices and medical panels. Despite significant progress, these systems still struggle to simultaneously meet the combined requirements of optical clarity, surface durability, and high AM efficacy on real-world touch interfaces.

In parallel, increasing attention has turned to the role of mechanical durability and fabrication scalability in nanostructured glass surfaces. Creating inverted nanostructures (nanoholes) in glass surfaces has been reported to improve the mechanical robustness of glass against lateral abrasion forces.^{37,38} Wang *et al.* demonstrated a robust superhydrophobic hierarchical micro- and nanoscale surface, in which the microscale “armor” protects the inner superhydrophobic nanoscale silica.³⁹ Their study successfully applied the scaffolding concept to metal, ceramic, and glass surfaces,

demonstrating the versatility of the design. In addition, a second key requirement for nanotextured surfaces in practical applications is that they can be fabricated using a straightforward, cost-effective method suitable for processing large-area substrates. Metal nanoparticles of Au, Ag, and Cu, generated via thermal dewetting, have recently been studied extensively because of their simple fabrication process and their capability to produce structures as small as a few tens of nanometers across large-area substrates. This method eliminates the need for time-consuming and complex e-beam or nanoimprint lithography.^{40–43} The nanoparticles are then directly used as etching masks via dry etching to create antireflective surfaces on glass⁴² or inverted structures (nanoholes) in both thin polymer films⁴¹ and glass,⁴³ which possess excellent mechanical durability and antireflective properties.

Recently, we reported a transparent and durable AM glass coating based on dewetted Cu nanoparticles.⁴⁴ While this approach offered promising AM performance and durability through protective capping layers, there still remains a need to enhance the mechanical durability and neutral color of the surface. To address these constraints, here we advance that concept by selectively embedding Cu at the bottom of nanoholes etched into glass using a lithography-free, wafer-compatible process: (i) thermal dewetting to define a metal-island mask, (ii) conversion to a polymer nanohole template, (iii) buffered oxide wet etching to form glass nanoholes, and (iv) deposition and liftoff to confine Cu inside the holes. The resulting surfaces exhibit average transmission of 80%–85% in the 380–750 nm range, haze <1%, and a near-neutral appearance ($\Delta E_{ab} \approx 3\text{--}4$ vs bare glass under D65). We evaluated antimicrobial performance under a BSL-1-compliant, modified EPA protocol as an initial proof-of-concept to illustrate the designed functionality, with broader pathogen testing and sanitizer-level validation planned for further investigations. The embedded Cu surfaces achieve $\approx 99\%$ reduction of *E. coli* OP50 after 1 h. Furthermore, abrasion tests using a crockmeter, simulating the action of a human finger, demonstrate that the embedded Cu remains protected within the nanoholes without measurable change in transmission or haze. Together, these results demonstrate a scalable, optically clear, and mechanically durable strategy for incorporating AM functionality into touch-based devices and transparent surfaces in healthcare and consumer environments.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Concept of embedding

The proposed design of transparent, abrasion-resistant glass surface is illustrated in Fig. 1(a). The embedded functional material at the base of the glass nanoholes is shielded from external tangential forces, such as those exerted by a human finger on a touchscreen. It is known that in the case of nanopillars, the higher and the thinner the nanostructures, the larger are the tangential and normal stresses due to physical contact with the surface.³⁷ Our design surface consisting of nanoholes, as opposed to nanopillars pointing upward, provides robustness and acts as the protective matrix for embedding the functional material. We have performed mechanical resistance tests using a crockmeter, which moves an abrasive cloth across the glass surface under a constant load, as depicted in Fig. 1(a).

FIG. 1. (a) Schematic illustration of the concept of a mechanically durable glass surface with an embedded functional material. The material is positioned below the surface plane, which an abrasive cloth traverses, demonstrating protection against wear. The dimensions are representative but not to scale, with randomness in the diameters and spacing of the holes. (b) Atomic force microscope (AFM) image of a typical nanostructure embedded with nominal 1.5 nm titanium (Ti) and 12 nm copper (Cu) nanodisks. The line profile across the nanohole (red arrow) indicates that the thickness of the embedded metal nanostructure is ~ 11 nm. The size of the scan is $1 \times 1 \mu\text{m}^2$, with a scale bar of 250 nm.

The atomic force microscope (AFM) scan shown in Fig. 1(b) reveals the morphology of the embedded nanostructures, which were fabricated by balancing several process trade-offs. These trade-offs will be thoroughly discussed in Sec. II B. Using the ImageJ tool for image processing and approximating the nanostructures as circular disks, we determined the diameter of the metal disks to be $\approx 182 \pm 28$ nm with 15% surface coverage. The inset in Fig. 1(b) shows an extracted cross-sectional profile of a single nanohole, indicating that the depth of the nanohole is ≈ 90 nm and the height of the embedded metal nanodisk is ≈ 11 nm.

B. Fabrication process and trade-offs

The novel fabrication process for creating embedded nanostructures in glass nanoholes is summarized in Fig. 2(a) and consists of six main steps (see Sec. III for all details). In the first step (i), a thin Ag film with a thickness of ~ 13 nm is sputtered onto the substrate and transformed into randomly sized and spaced Ag nanoparticles (AgNPs) via rapid thermal annealing. Ag was selected to define the nanostructure morphology because it readily dewets into rounded nanoislands on glass^{43,45} and its straightforward removal using ammonium persulfate. Our group has previously employed randomly distributed nanoislands of Cu^{41,44,46} and Ag,^{43,45} formed through rapid thermal annealing, to create nanoscale patterns on large-area glass surfaces for various applications. This method circumvents the costly and time-intensive lithography typically required for micro- and nano-structuring. By adjusting the initial Ag film thickness, annealing duration, and temperature, the spacing, size, and density of the resulting nanofeatures can be controlled, as detailed in our previous work.⁴³ The morphology of the AgNPs with initial thickness of 13 nm is shown in the AFM scan in Fig. 2(b). A histogram of the Ag nanoparticle diameters extracted from the AFM image is shown in Fig. S1(a) (supplementary material), with a mean diameter of 175 ± 69 nm and height of 53 ± 10 nm. Table S1 (supplementary material) summarizes the nanostructure morphological parameters. A key

(and a first) trade-off in nanoparticle sizing is that larger AgNPs lead to increased scattering losses of the final nanostructures in the target optical range, as indicated by higher haze values. Conversely, smaller and shorter nanoparticles may be fully embedded in the subsequent polymer mask, making them inaccessible to chemical etching. The optimal Ag deposition times for the subsequent processing steps were determined to be 35–45 s, corresponding to 11–15 nm-thick films.

In the second step (ii), the substrate with the AgNPs is treated with hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS), a primer that renders the glass surface hydrophobic. This treatment ensures better adhesion between the subsequently spun diluted polymer and the glass surface. To obtain a polymer thickness less than the average height of the AgNPs, the dilution ratio was optimized while keeping the spin coating time and speed constant. Figure S2(a) (supplementary material) shows the distribution of the polymer thickness across a calibration Si wafer, determined by fitting a model to the reflectance data. The average thickness was $\approx 35.5 \pm 0.2$ nm. At this step, the key trade-off was achieving a polymer layer thin enough to expose the tops of the AgNPs for subsequent wet etching, while ensuring the polymer mask was thick enough to withstand both the wet etch of the AgNPs and the required glass etching durations that followed.

In the third step (iii), the AgNPs are chemically etched using ammonium persulfate in a sonicator, forming a polymer nanohole mask, as shown in Fig. 2(c). The masks were characterized with AFM, and an average depth of $\approx 34.4 \pm 1.1$ nm was determined by extracting the line profiles across multiple holes, as illustrated in Fig. S2(b). The mean diameter of the polymer nanoholes of $\approx 140 \pm 49$ nm [Fig. S1(b), Table S1] is smaller than the mean AgNP diameter because the resist partially buries the particles. The wet etch fully removes the Ag material but the hole diameter reflects the nanoparticle cross section at the resist surface rather than the full particle diameter.

In the fourth step (iv), samples are treated with buffered oxide etch (BOE) to isotropically etch the glass beneath the polymer mask, forming glass nanoholes. The surface morphology of the polymer

mask immediately following this process is shown in Fig. 2(d). The depth of the glass nanoholes was controlled by the etching duration. Calibration samples were treated for durations ranging from 1 to 5 min, after which the polymer was stripped off with acetone. AFM line profiles were measured across multiple individual nanoholes, revealing an etch rate for the fused silica of ≈ 30 nm/min. Another key trade-off at this stage of the fabrication process is the optimal etch duration. The isotropic etching nature of the BOE solution enlarges the lateral dimensions of the glass nanoholes [see Fig. S1(c) and Table S1], which increases scattering losses. In addition, larger undercuts beneath the polymer mask facilitate the subsequent liftoff process. Conversely, excessively long etching can cause the polymer mask to peel off. We found that optimal etch durations were between 2 and 3 min.

In the next step (v), e-beam deposition is used to fill the bottom of the glass nanoholes with the embedded functional material, which may consist of a single layer or a stack of several layers. E-beam deposition is chosen over other techniques, such as sputtering, to create a less conformal layer that does not cover the edges and undercuts of the polymer. This approach enhances the liftoff process and results in a high surface yield of removed polymer. Cu, which provides AM activity, is used as the functional material. Due

to its poor adhesion to glass surfaces,⁴⁷ a 2 nm titanium (Ti) adhesion layer is first deposited. In the final step (vi), the liftoff of metal on top of the polymer mask is performed by sonicating the samples in acetone for up to 5 min, followed by rinsing with isopropanol and drying with nitrogen. The morphology of the final embedded nanostructures is shown in Fig. 2(e). Statistics for the glass nanohole and embedded Cu feature sizes were acquired on an independent, identically processed batch and are provided in Fig. S1(c) and Table S1 (supplementary material). The glass nanohole diameters exceed the Cu nanodisk diameters since the metal preferentially accumulates at the hole bottom while the sidewalls remain largely uncoated. In our process, the practical upper limit for the embedded Cu thickness was ~ 15 – 17 nm (nominal) since the thicker films did not lift off reliably.

C. Optical and structural properties

Considering all the trade-offs in the previously described fabrication process, the optical transmission and morphology of a set fabricated with optimized parameters is presented in Fig. 3. These parameters, along with the average transmission in the 380–800 nm range and the haze of the embedded nanostructures in the visible

FIG. 2. (a) Summary of the fabrication process for embedding nanostructures in glass. (i) A sputtered Ag film is thermally dewetted, forming a plurality of randomly arranged Ag nanoparticles (AgNPs) across the substrate surface. (ii) The substrate is primed with hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS), and a diluted polymer film is spun on. (iii) The AgNPs are wet-etched with ammonium persulfate in a warm ultrasonication bath, producing a polymer nanohole mask. (iv) Nanoholes in the glass are formed after buffered oxide etch (BOE) treatment. (v) Electron beam deposition of the embedded material, followed by a liftoff step in acetone (vi) results in embedded material nanodisks residing at the bottom of the glass nanoholes. Corresponding atomic force microscopy images of the dewetted AgNPs (b), the polymer nanohole mask (c), the mask immediately after BOE etching (d), and the embedded material nanostructures (e) are provided. All scans are $2 \times 2 \mu\text{m}^2$, with a scale bar of 500 nm; the color scale shows height (z) in nm.

FIG. 3. Optical and structural properties of the embedded nanostructures. (a) Transmission in the 380–800 nm range of a set of five samples with embedded Ti/Cu nanostructure in glass nanoholes. The inset photos compare the transparency and the difference in color appearance ΔE_{ab} between the flat unstructured glass and the embedded nanostructure (sample E). Fabrication parameters are listed in Table I. Scanning electron microscope (SEM) images of the nanostructured surface in secondary (b) and back scattered electron modes [(c) and (d)]. The scale bar in panels (b) and (c) is 500 nm, while 250 nm in panel (d). The presence of Ti and Cu is evident from the energy dispersive x-ray (EDX) spectrum shown in panel (e).

TABLE I. Summary of the parameters that define the morphology of the embedded nanostructures and their optical performance.

Sample id	Sputtering (s)	RTA at 750 °C (s)	APS etch (min)	BOE etch (min)	Ti/Cu (nm)	Liftoff (s)	T_{avg} (%)	Haze (%)
A	40	135	20	2.5	2/12	90	84.84	0.91
B	40	135	20	2.5	2/12	90	84.53	0.85
C	40	135	20	2.5	2/12	70	84.40	0.77
D	40	135	20	2.5	2/12	105	82.50	0.64
E	40	135	20	2.5	2/12	90	85.30	0.85

range, are listed in Table I. As shown in Fig. 3(a), the transmission of all samples remains above 80% across the measured range, with a peak at ≈ 590 nm. This peak is attributed to the inherent properties of the dielectric function of the thin Cu film, particularly its interband transition threshold energy at 2.1 eV.^{48,49} The extracted color coordinates in the CIELAB color space, summarized in Table S2 in the supplementary material, show that the difference in color perception between the bare glass and the Cu nanostructures, quantified by ΔE_{ab} metric, is within a 3–4 range. While values slightly exceed the $\Delta E_{ab} < 3$ guideline commonly cited for color-critical consumer display applications, they remain near the perceptibility threshold. Such values are well within the acceptable range for applications such as protective coatings, touchscreen surfaces, and non-color-calibrated optical interfaces, where ΔE_{ab} values up to 5 are generally considered acceptable. In addition, the colorless appearance of the samples is demonstrated by comparing photos of unstructured glass and sample E in the inset of Fig. 3(a). Overall, the average transmission above 84%, although slightly lower than the 92% transmittance of standard display glass due to the added Cu-based functionality, along with haze values below 1% for all five samples highlight their potential suitability for touchscreen device applications. Process scalability is further supported by sample-to-sample uniformity within a single batch (Fig. S3, supplementary material), where nanohole diameter and density distributions are consistent across three identically

processed samples and their transmission spectra overlap with a common localized surface plasmon resonance dip at $\lambda_{res} = 986 \pm 7$ nm ($n = 3$).

The morphology of the embedded Ti/Cu nanostructures is further illustrated by the scanning electron microscope (SEM) image shown in Fig. 3(b). This sample was treated with BOE for 3.5 min, and the nominal thickness of the Ti/Cu layer was 2 and 15 nm, respectively. The compositional contrast image shown in Fig. 3(c) demonstrates the distribution of the metal (bright regions) at the bottom of the glass nanoholes. The depth of the nanohole and the thickness of the embedded Ti/Cu layer measured from the cross-sectional image in panel (d) are ≈ 100 nm and ≈ 18 nm, respectively, in good agreement with the nominal values. The embedded surface was probed with an energy dispersive x-ray detector and peaks corresponding to Cu and Ti were identified, as displayed in Fig. 3(e).

D. Antimicrobial efficacy and mechanical durability

To assess the AM performance of the embedded Cu nanostructures, we tested *E. coli* OP50, a non-pathogenic laboratory strain compatible with biosafety level 1 (BSL-1) facilities and widely used as the standard Gram-negative food bacterium in *C. elegans* metal and nanotoxicology assays.^{50–52} The testing protocol was

adapted from the U.S. EPA method for evaluating the sanitizing efficacy of Cu alloy surfaces (see Sec. III). Although standardized test strains such as *S. aureus* were not accessible due to current laboratory constraints, the results provide an initial functional validation of AM activity within the embedded architecture. Testing against BSL-2 pathogens would be a natural extension to directly benchmark sanitizer performance. All samples used in the AM test were treated with BOE for 2.5 min to form glass nano-holes of ~80 nm depth with embedded Ti/Cu bilayers of 2 and 12 nm thickness, respectively. To modulate Cu ion release, a subset of samples was coated with a 20 nm-thick SiO₂ overlayer by electron-beam deposition. These structural parameters were kept consistent across the test set to isolate the effect of the capping layer on Cu ion diffusion and AM response.

Figure 4(a) presents the log reduction (LR) in viable bacterial counts following 1 h of contact with four representative surfaces: unstructured glass (negative control), a bulk Cu coupon (positive control), embedded Cu nanostructures without a capping layer, and embedded Cu nanostructures capped with 20 nm of SiO₂. The LR is calculated as the negative base-10 logarithm of the ratio between the geometric mean of colony-forming units (CFUs) recovered from the structured surface and those from the unstructured glass control, following the EPA definition⁵³ (supplementary material, Sec. 3). Across three independent tests on different days, the average LR values were 7.01 ± 0.18 for the Cu coupon, 1.94 ± 0.69 for the uncapped embedded Cu structures, and 0.43 ± 0.34 for the capped configuration, corresponding to approximate reductions of 100%, 99%, and 63% relative to glass, respectively. While the embedded Cu samples do not reach the EPA sanitizer benchmark of ≥ 3 LR at 60 min, the ~2 LR observed for the uncapped nanostructure at this contact time provides a clear functional indicator of antimicrobial activity and a basis for design optimization via increasing the amount of available copper, geometry, or release control through capping overlayers. The unstructured glass control showed no measurable bactericidal

effect, confirming that the AM activity is linked to the presence and configuration of Cu in the structured surfaces.

In parallel, inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS) was used to quantify the concentration of Cu ions released into the test medium under identical conditions without microbial loading [Fig. 4(a), right axis]. The measured ion concentrations were 15.2 ± 1.5 mg/l for the Cu coupon, 13.0 ± 1.4 mg/l for the uncapped embedded Cu, and 4.98 ± 0.13 mg/l for the SiO₂-capped sample with standard deviations calculated from $n = 6, 5,$ and 2 measurements, respectively. These values align with the LR trend, supporting an ion-mediated contribution to the AM effect. The concentrations are comparable with reported inhibitory ranges for Cu against *E. coli*, which typically range from 1 to 4 mg/l depending on ion speciation and environmental conditions.^{24,44} In our study, both the Cu coupon and uncapped embedded Cu exceeded these ranges, yielding high ion concentration values. The capped sample, while still above minimum inhibitory concentration, produced a lower LR due to the diffusion-limiting effect of the SiO₂ overlayer. This difference in release profile highlights the potential to modulate AM performance through surface engineering and shows that SiO₂ capping controls Cu ion availability and, consequently, the LR. As future work, quantifying the Cu ion release over time by ICP-MS during repeated exposures and comparing LR before and after each cycle would provide further insight into the kinetics and long-term AM performance. Varying the SiO₂ capping layer thickness to evaluate the expected balance between ion release rate and antimicrobial performance will also be necessary.

Touchscreens are subject to frequent contact and wear. Therefore, their mechanical robustness and ability to withstand general wear and tear are vital. As introduced in Fig. 1(a), the crockmeter test is a relevant method for assessing the reliability of the nanostructures.⁵⁴ The tested sample was treated with BOE for 3 min; the Ti/Cu bilayer was 2 and 14 nm and had a 25 nm SiO₂

FIG. 4. (a) Antimicrobial (AM) activity of Ti/Cu embedded nanostructures against *E. coli* OP50 without and with a silica capping layer. The bars on the left axis show the mean \log_{10} reduction (LR) obtained from $n = 3$ independent tests; the error bars represent the standard deviation (SD). The dashed line denotes the EPA sanitizer criterion ($\text{LR} \geq 3$). A glass control (no Cu) is included at $\text{LR} = 0$. The killing efficiency decreases when silica is present, consistent with reduced Cu ions release quantified by ICP-MS (right axis). The blue points represent the mean \pm SD. (b) Optical transmission before (red) and after (blue) a crockmeter test involving 2000 double strokes with a constant load. The sample has a 25 nm SiO₂ protective layer. After the abrasion test, it was cleaned with O₂ plasma to remove cheesecloth residuals. (c) SEM images of the abraded surface in panel (b): a low magnification ($\times 2.5\text{k}$) tilted secondary electron image (top) of the area where the crockmeter head moved, demonstrating the overall resistance of the nanostructure. Cu remains intact inside the holes, as shown in the backscattered electron image. The scale bar is 10 μm (top) and 500 nm (bottom), respectively.

overlayer. The crockmeter test consisted of 2000 double passes with a constant load of 9 N over a contact area of 2 cm² using a standard cheesecloth fabric. The comparison in transmission in the 380–750 nm range before (red) and after (blue) the abrasion test is shown in Fig. 4(b). Note that the surface was O₂ plasma that was cleaned to remove the cheesecloth residuals transferred during the abrasion (see Fig. S4 in the [supplementary material](#)). The virtual overlap of the spectra before and after indicates that the embedded nanostructure remained structurally intact after the test. The low-magnification SEM scan of the abraded area shown in Fig. 4(c) (top) reveals the overall resistance of the surface with little marks of where the crockmeter head moved along. The cross-section image shown in Fig. 4(c) (bottom) confirms that the embedded Cu remains inside the nanoholes, successfully protected from the surface abrasion. Post-abrasion antimicrobial and Cu ion release tests were not performed in this study. In follow-up work, Cu ion release and LR before and after abrasion will be quantified to evaluate the long-term functional durability of the embedded nanostructures.

III. METHODS

A. Fabrication of embedded nanostructures in glass nanoholes

1. Formation of silver nanoislands mask

Double-sided, optically polished, high-purity fused silica substrates (Corning 8655) with a size of 2 × 2 in² and 1 mm thickness were ultrasonically cleaned in acetone and isopropanol for 10 min each and dried with nitrogen. Direct current (DC) magnetron sputtering (ATC Orion 8, AJA International, Inc.) from a 3-in. Ag target was used to coat the samples. Before all depositions, an argon (Ar) plasma cleaning step [50 W bias power and 40 standard cubic centimeter per minute (sccm) at 5 × 10⁻³ Torr] for 5 min was performed in the main chamber to further clean the samples. Ultrathin Ag films were deposited at room temperature, 2 × 10⁻³ Torr working pressure, 75 W DC power, and 20 sccm pure Ar flow. The chamber base pressure was 10⁻⁸ Torr; the distance between the substrate and the target was 32 cm; and the rotation speed set at 40 rpm. Using ellipsometric fitting (J. A. Woollam Company) of five Ag films with increasing deposition times, the deposition rate at the described conditions was determined to be 0.33 nm/s. The Ag-coated substrates were then annealed at 750 °C for 135 s in a rapid thermal annealing system (Tsunami™ RTP600S), resulting in dewetting of the Ag films into round-shaped nanosized islands. To prevent oxidation of films in the oven, a mixture of hydrogen (4%) and nitrogen was blown inside it. Substrates were cooled down to room temperature by nitrogen flow for 20 min. The distribution in size, height, and separation of the formed nanoislands is controlled by the initial thickness of the Ag film.

2. Formation of polymer nanoholes mask

The substrates with the dewetted Ag nanoislands were dehydrated at 150 °C in an oven, and a hexamethyldisilazane (HMDS) adhesion promoter was vapor deposited in the same oven (Yield Engineering Systems). Next, a positive photoresist (ma-P1205, Micro Resist Technology), diluted with propylene glycol methyl ether acetate (PGMEA) in a 1:5 ratio, was spin-coated onto the substrate for 30 s at 5000 rpm. This was followed by a soft bake

on a hotplate at 100 °C for 1 min. The initial calibration of the polymer thickness was performed by mapping it on a 100 mm silicon (Si) wafer using a reflectometer (F50, Filmetrics). To create the nanoholes in the polymer, wet etching of the Ag nanoislands was carried out by ultrasonication in a 15% (w/w) aqueous ammonium persulfate solution (APS-100, Transene) for 25 to 60 min at an elevated temperature of 40 to 45 °C (Branson 8510 Ultrasonic Cleaner).

3. Embedding of functional material in glass nanoholes

Prior to etching the glass with buffered oxide etchant (BOE 20:1, 38% NH₄F, 2% HF, 60% H₂O, Transene), substrates were hard-baked at 150 °C for 15 min in an oven to further increase the adhesion between the glass surface and the polymer mask. A protective foil was applied to the unmasked side to prevent etching. The slides were then treated in the BOE solution for intervals between 1 and 5 min, cleaned with deionized water, and dried. Next, the deposition of the functional material was carried out in an electron beam evaporator (Angstrom Engineering) at room temperature, with base pressure of $\approx 2 \times 10^{-7}$ Torr, and 60 rpm rotation speed. First, a Ti film of 1.5–2.0 nm was deposited at the rate of 1 Å/s with the aim to provide better adhesion of the subsequent Cu layer. Without breaking the vacuum, 99.99% pure Cu films with thicknesses ranging between 10 and 15 nm were deposited. The deposition pressure was $\approx 2 \times 10^{-6}$ Torr, and the rate of 1 Å/s was monitored by a quartz microbalance crystal. Finally, to remove the polymer mask and the metal on top, a liftoff process was performed by immersing the substrates in acetone and ultrasonically cleaning them for 1–5 min. Occasionally, additional spraying with acetone under air pressure was needed to ensure complete removal of the polymer. Samples were subsequently rinsed with isopropanol and dried with nitrogen. SiO₂ capping layers were deposited at 1 Å/s in the same e-beam chamber, maintaining all the same conditions as those used for the metals.

B. Optical, morphological, and durability characterization

The directional transmission spectra were acquired in the wavelength range of 380–2000 nm by using a UV–vis–NIR spectrophotometer (Perkin Elmer LAMBDA 1050) at 0° angle of incidence. The scattering of the surfaces in the vis region was quantified by measuring the haze parameter, that is, the amount of incident light diffused by the sample at an angle larger than 2.5° divided by total light transmitted by the sample, with a hazemeter (Haze-Gard I, BYK Gardner). Three measurements at different points of each sample were taken, and the average and standard deviation were reported. The morphology of the nanostructured surfaces was examined using a field-emission scanning electron microscope (FE-SEM, Hitachi SU-70) operating in both secondary electron and back scattered electron modes at 5 kV and equipped with an energy dispersive x-ray spectroscopy (EDS) detector. The surfaces and the polymer mask were additionally characterized by atomic force microscopy (AFM) in tapping mode (Veeco Dimension Icon-PT). The mechanical durability of the structures was tested using a crockmeter (M238BB, SDL Atlas) with a special cloth used in the standard test 8 approved by the American Association of Textile Chemists and

Colorists (AATCC). The abrading surface was 2 cm^2 with a constant applied force of 9 N. Each cycle consists of two single passes with the stroke length of 50 mm.

C. Antimicrobial testing protocol

The AM testing protocol was adapted from the U.S. EPA method for evaluating the sanitizing efficacy of Cu alloy surfaces.⁵³ Due to BSL-1 laboratory constraints, standard test strains (*Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538 and *Enterobacter aerogenes* ATCC 13048) were not used. Instead, *Escherichia coli* OP50, a non-pathogenic BSL-1 compliant strain, was used as a model organism for preliminary evaluation. Test samples, along with uncoated glass and Cu coupon controls, were immersed in a 70% ethanol solution for 5 min, rinsed with deionized (DI) water, and subsequently, sterilized under ultraviolet (UV) light for 15 min. For bacterial culture preparation, a single isolated colony of *E. coli* OP50 was inoculated into 15 ml of Luria-Bertani (LB) broth and incubated overnight at 37°C in an orbital shaker (Thermo Fisher MaxQ800). The bacterial concentration was estimated by measuring the optical density at 600 nm (OD_{600}) using a Nanodrop 2000c spectrophotometer (Thermo Fisher Scientific). To prepare the inoculum, the overnight culture was diluted in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) to a final concentration of 1.0×10^8 colony-forming units (CFU)/ml. To 4700 μl of this suspension, 250 μl of fetal bovine serum (FBS) and 50 μl of Triton X-100 were added. FBS was included as a general growth supplement, while Triton X-100 was used to facilitate uniform spreading. A $1 \times 1\text{ in.}^2$ area was marked at the center of each sample, and 20 μl of the inoculum was evenly applied using bent sterile pipette tips. The samples were left to dry under ambient conditions for ~ 15 min and subsequently incubated in closed Petri dishes for 1 h at room temperature. Samples were then immersed in 5 ml of Lethen broth and shaken at 100 rpm for 3 min to recover adhered bacteria. The resulting suspension was serially diluted tenfold, and 100 μl aliquots from each dilution were plated in duplicate onto tryptic soy agar (TSA) plates. The plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 h, and bacterial colonies were counted to quantify viable cells. Log reduction values were calculated based on the difference between the logarithm (base 10) of the average CFU counts recovered from the test samples and those recovered from the uncoated glass control following the EPA-defined protocol. A ≥ 3 log reduction ($\geq 99.9\%$) relative to the control is required for the test surface to qualify as a sanitizer after the specified 60-min exposure. Details of the calculation method are provided in the [supplementary material](#).

D. Copper ion release rates

The concentration of the released Cu ions into a mock solution was determined using inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometry (ICP-MS). Briefly, 4700 μl phosphate-buffered saline (PBS), 250 μl fetal bovine serum (FBS), and 50 μl TritonX surfactant were mixed and 20 μl of the solution was spread on the central $1 \times 1\text{ in.}^2$ area of the embedded with Cu sample. The samples dried in ~ 15 min and were kept at relative humidity of $\approx 10\%$ and temperature of 21°C for 2 h. The leachate from the nanostructured surface was collected by rinsing the exposed region with $2 \times 150\text{ }\mu\text{l}$ of PBS and transferring the rinse solution into a vial. Along with the Cu

embedded samples, positive and negative controls were run with pure Cu coupons and PBS solution, respectively.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The widespread use of high-touch transparent surfaces in public and healthcare environments demands materials that combine optical clarity, mechanical robustness, and AM function. We addressed this challenge by developing a scalable method to create a durable, transparent, AM glass surface by embedding Cu nanodisks in glass nanoholes. Thermally dewetted Ag nanoislands defined an inverse pattern in a thin polymer mask (nanoholes), which was used in a BOE etch process to create 80–100 nm nanoholes in the glass. AM Cu was deposited at the base of the nanoholes; the excess metal and polymer mask were then lifted off, leaving the Cu recessed below the wear plane. By balancing fabrication trade-offs, the optimized surfaces exhibit an average transmittance $>80\%$ across 380–750 nm, haze $<1\%$, and a minimal perceptual color shift $\Delta E_{ab} \approx 3.4$. AM tests following a modified US EPA protocol showed reduction close to 99% against *E. coli* within 1 h, attributable to release and dissolution of Cu ions. Crockmeter tests caused no noticeable change in transmission or morphology; SEM scans confirmed that the Cu remained intact inside the holes, demonstrating robustness for high-touch environments. The process is compatible with large-area manufacturing and can accommodate alternative functional stacks, for example, fragile porous materials or other metal combinations, making it a strong candidate for future applications in touch-activated public and personal displays. Future work will explore geometry optimization and strain-specific validation to further enhance efficacy and move toward regulatory thresholds for sanitizer designation.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

The [supplementary material](#) encompasses the following: Fig. S1 presents the nanostructure sizes at successive fabrication stages; Table S1 summarizes the geometrical parameters of the nanostructures; Fig. S2 presents the thickness and morphology of the nanoholes polymer mask; Fig. S3 demonstrates sample-to-sample variation and reproducibility; Table S2 summarizes the CIELAB color coordinates extraction from transmission spectra; and Fig. S4 shows SEM images of the abraded nanostructure right after the crockmeter test.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare the following competing financial interest(s): I.K., W.S., P.M., and V.P. are co-inventors in a patent application related to the results of this paper.

Author Contributions

I.K. designed and conducted the experiments, analyzed the data, prepared the figures, and wrote the original draft. R.H. performed the antimicrobial (A.M.) testing and analysis, and contributed to writing and editing the manuscript. A.M. developed the A.M. testing protocol and assisted with the tests and analysis. W.S. and P.M. provided supervision and assisted with manuscript editing. V.P. conceived the original idea, contributed to data analysis, supervised the experimental work, secured funding, and participated in manuscript revision. All authors contributed to the review and editing of the manuscript and approved the final version.

Iliyan Karadzhov: Conceptualization (supporting); Data curation (lead); Formal analysis (lead); Investigation (lead); Methodology (equal); Visualization (lead); Writing – original draft (lead); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Rubaiya Hussain:** Data curation (supporting); Formal analysis (equal); Investigation (supporting); Methodology (supporting); Writing – original draft (supporting); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Alessia Mezzadrelli:** Data curation (supporting); Formal analysis (supporting); Investigation (supporting); Methodology (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Wageesha Senaratne:** Conceptualization (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Prantik Mazumder:** Conceptualization (equal); Resources (equal); Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal). **Valerio Pruneri:** Conceptualization (lead); Formal analysis (supporting); Funding acquisition (lead); Supervision (equal); Writing – review & editing (equal).

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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